

agro BRIDGES

**“Building bridges between consumers and producers
by supporting short food supply chains through a
systemic, holistic, multi-actor approach-based Toolbox”**

(Grant Agreement 101000788)

COORDINATION AND SUPPORT ACTION

“Let’s meet!” Event Validation Report

Responsible Partner: VTT

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“Let’s meet!” Event Validation Report Finland

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1. Introduction

The present report summarises the activities of VTT for the organisation and validation of the **“Yhteistyötä voimaa lyhyisiin elintarvikeketjuihin” - “Cooperation gives strength to short food supply chains” event in Hämeenlinna, Finland on 14.2.2023**. This event is one of the four “Let’s meet!” event concepts designed in agroBRIDGES Task 3.4 for the local promotion of Short Food Supply Chains (SFSC), locally produced food and involved market actors, namely (i) Producer Events, (ii) Culinary Events, (iii) Celebrate local heroes / SFSCs, and (iv) Open Days. This event was a Producer Event. The organisation, planning and implementation of the event was performed using the guidelines and templates designed by FBCD to enable actors in the agri-food sector in replicating the events in their local agri-food ecosystems.

The present report outlines all steps taken for the design, planning and implementation of the regional event, as well as the outcomes and evaluation of the event by the participants and the organising agroBRIDGES partner, to produce suggestions for the improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool. The remainder of the report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2** – Describing the concept selection, design, organisation, and implementation of the “Yhteistyötä voimaa lyhyisiin elintarvikeketjuihin” event in Hämeenlinna, Finland on 14.2.2023.
- **Chapter 3** – Outlining the validation results for the events by participants and the value found in the “Let’s meet!” guidelines by the organising partners when creating and launching their event.
- **Chapter 4** – Concluding remarks for the event and suggestions for improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool.

2. “Let’s meet!” event organisation details

2.1 Concept selection and definition of activities (programme)

The selected “Let’s meet” event concept in Finland was the **Producer Event**. During the MAP process in WP1 it was noticed that having the producers to be involved in different activities is quite challenging. Thus, we ended up joining efforts with another national project that also concentrates on local food and having more close dialogue between farmers, consumers, and retailers (<https://www.hamk.fi/lahiruokadialogi>).

The event was held on Valentine’s Day on February 14th, 2023, from 9:30 to 13:00. We started the event with morning coffee at 9:30. The first presentation was at 10:00 and it was held by **Mirva Lampinen from VTT**. She is leading the Food & Beyond collective (<https://foodandbeyond.eu/>) and told us what the impact of the networks in the collaboration in the food sector is. The second presentation was held by the representatives of the national project that we collaborated the event with. They have just published their handbook “The path of local food to the store and to the consumer's shopping basket - a guide for local food producers and retailers” (<https://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-951-784-840-4>, in Finnish only) and they presented some highlights from the handbook. The third presentation was a short introduction to the agroBRIDGES project and to the toolbox highlighting a few tools. Then we had a short 5-minute presentations from 7 producers, 2 retail representatives and 3 companies (see table 1 below for more details). The aim was that they will give a short introduction and during the networking part participants can have more detailed discussions with them.

Table 1: Event programme

Title of activity	Short description	Date & Time (local)	Location
	We started the event with coffee. People had a chance to meet each other as well as set up their table for product or company presentations.	9:30 - 10:00	Design factory, Häme university of applied science, Hämeenlinna
Welcome	Welcoming people and short introduction of the event by organisers.	10:00 - 10:10	
Keynote speech: “The importance of networks in cooperation.”	Mirva Lampinen from VTT gave a presentation about creating networks and what is their role in collaboration in the food sector.	10:10 - 11:30	
Presentation: The path of local food to the store and to the consumer's shopping basket - a guide for local food producers and retailers.	Short introduction of the handbook released by the national project with which we arranged the event.	10:30 - 10:45	

Title of activity	Short description	Date & Time (local)	Location
Presentation: agroBRIDGES project and toolbox	A brief presentation of the agroBRIDGES project and the toolbox highlighting a few tools.	10:45 - 11:00	
Short presentations of producers, representatives of retailers and companies participating in the event.	Some of the producers and companies were invited to have a presentation in the event. In addition, while participants registered for the event, we asked them whether they would like to have a short presentation of their business related to the SFSC in the event.	11:00 - 12:15	
Networking	Companies and especially producers had the opportunity to present, taste and sell their products. In addition, other companies had the opportunity to discuss their business with the participants.	12:15 - 13:00 (actually last producers left at 15:00)	

2.2 Location, Venue/Space selection and arrangements

The event was held at the premises of **Häme university of applied science in Hämeenlinna**. Pictures of the venue can be seen in Figure 1. The reason for the selection of the space was that the national project we collaborated with was led by this university and they had premises specifically designed for holding different kinds of events: **the Design factory**. There was plenty of room for networking, but most importantly, tables available for the participants to set up presenting their products. In addition, the location of Hämeenlinna is easily accessible from different parts of Finland by train, bus or car.

The venue was booked two months before the event to ensure its availability. Coffee service was booked two weeks before the event and confirmed a few days before.

Figure 1: Pictures of the venue

2.3 Personnel involved in the organisation of the event

For the organisation of the event, effort distribution has been made between VTT and Häme university of applied sciences. From VTT two persons participated actively in planning and organising the event. Also, one person took care of the event's registration form. In addition, two other persons from VTT were asked to give presentations in the event.

From Häme university of applied science one person participated actively in planning and organising the event. In addition, the university cafeteria took care of the catering.

In the event the producers had an essential role. These producers were willing to present (7), taste or sell (8) their products in the event. The products presented in the event included e.g., different kinds of jams, juices, flour and flakes, chocolate, honey, and pickled vegetables. Table 2 summarises the estimated effort and expertise needed for the event organisation.

Table 2: Estimated effort and expertise needed for the event

Specialisation	Number of employees	Expected role	In-house / External	Estimated effort (person days)
Organisers, VTT	2	Development of promotional material, contact with participants, communication in social networks, presence at the event and presentation, material purchase	In-house	5
Organisers, Häme university of applied sciences	1	Communication in social networks, contact with participants, presence, and presentation at the event	External	N/A
Assistant, VTT	1	Taking care of the registration form	In-house	1
Producers	8	Contribution and explanation of products at the event	External	N/A
People that gave presentation in the event	19	Preparing and keeping the presentations in the event	In-house (4) External (15)	N/A
Catering	N/A	Food and drinks for guests	External	N/A

2.4 Event material

The material used to promote and market the event is shown and described below, see figures 2 and 3. The templates developed by the agroBRIDGES project were used as a basis for making these materials.

During the event the handbook which was published by the project we cooperated with was delivered to the participants. In addition, the Häme university of applied science as well as some of the producers offered brochures for participants.

Figure 2: The event invitation and program

VTT
HAMK | Bio RESEARCH UNIT
Kauppa valmennus

Yhteistyöstä voimaa lyhyisiin elintarvikeketjuihin

**Ystävänpäivänä tiistaina
14.2.2023
klo 9.30–12.30 Hämeenlinna**

Lyhyisiin elintarvikeketjuihin ja paikallisiin lähiruokamarkkinoihin keskittyvä tapahtuma kokoo ystävänpäivänä yhteen lähiruokatuottajia, kuluttajia, kaupan edustajia sekä muita ruokaketjun toimijoita. Tilaisuudessa keskustellaan verkostojen yhteistyön merkityksestä ja kuullaan lyhyitä elintarvikeketjuja tukevista toimintatavoista.

MIKSI OSALLISTUA TAPAHTUMAAN?

- Tapahtuma tarjoaa erinomaisen mahdollisuuden esittäytyä ja luoda tulevaisuuden yhteistyöverkostoja.
- Alan toimijoilla on mahdollisuus olla esillä ständillä ja/tai lyhyellä puheenvuorolla, myös tuotteiden maistattaminen on mahdollista.
- Kuulet, millaisia työkaluja ja toimintatapoja on luotu lyhyiden elintarvikeketjujen tukemiseksi.
- Saat mukaasi Lähiruuan tie kauppaan ja kuluttajan ostoskoriin -oppaan.

Paikka:
Hämeen ammattikorkeakoulu
Design Factory (E-rakennus)
Visamäentie 35 E
13100 Hämeenlinna
[HAMK Hämeenlinna aluekartta](https://www.hamk.fi/aluekartta)

ILMOITTAUDU TAPAHTUMAAN TÄSTÄ
Viimeistään ti 7.2.

VTT
HAMK | Bio RESEARCH UNIT
Kauppa valmennus

Yhteistyöstä voimaa lyhyisiin elintarvikeketjuihin 14.2.2023

OHJELMA

9.30 Aamukahvi

10.00 Tervetuloa
Verkostojen yhteistyön merkitys
Mirva Lampinen, VTT
Lähiruuan tie kauppaan ja kuluttajan ostoskoriin
Sanna Lento, HAMK; Juha Ketola, Kauppavalmennus; Anu Seisto, VTT
Lyhyitä elintarvikeketjuja tukevat agroBRIDGES työkalut
Kaisa Vehmas & Minna Kulju, VTT

11.05 Yritysesittelyt ja lyhyet puheenvuorot

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Helena Tiiliä, Pajuparvi Helena Tiiliä, Pälkäne
Otti Koskinen, Hakolan marjatila, Turenki
Paola Guerrero de Cohen, Ainoa Winery, Hollola
Tanja Eliander, Pt-myyntipääliikkö, Prisma HML
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Jani Kasanen, toimitusjohtaja, Second Thought Oy
Heli Nykänen, Package Testing & Research Oy
Juho-Matias Lehtonen, Vaskio Oy

n. 12.05-12.30 Verkostoitumista

Lisätietoa tilaisuuden järjestävistä hankkeista:
agroBRIDGES: <https://www.agrobridges.eu/>
Hämäläinen lähiruokadialogi: <https://www.hamk.fi/lahiruokadialogi/>

Euroopan maaseudun kehittämisen maatalousrahasto: Eurooppa investoi maaseutalueisiin

Hanke on saanut rahoitusta Euroopan Unionin Horizon 2020 tutkimus- ja innovaatio-ohjelmasta sopimuksen nro 101000788 mukaisesti.

Figure 3: The social media ad of the event

Figure 4: The cover page of the handbook delivered in the event

Figure 5: The table with name tags, event program and brochures

2.5 Engagement of contributors and collaborators

Last October we entered up in a discussion to arrange the event in collaboration with the national project that also focuses on local food. The objective of this project was fostering communication and cooperation between local producers, consumers, and retailers. The national project was ending at the beginning of 2023, and they were planning to have a final event to present their project results and handbook. Thus, we concluded that it is not reasonable to arrange multiple events with similar topics as well as for the same audience and decided to have this event together with these two projects.

At first, we discussed which kind of content would benefit producers and what would make them interested in participating in the event. In addition, we started planning the topics of presentations, inviting speakers under these topics as well as inviting companies, retailers, and producers to attend the event. We decided to have producers as the main presenters and especially producers that had some experience of short food supply chains and they could present how SFSC relates to their business and what kind of experience they have on it. In addition, we wanted to have representatives of retailers to talk about their role in enhancing SFSCs and supporting producers.

The first speakers/presenters were contacted at the very beginning of December. In addition, at the beginning of January 2023 the MAP members of Finland were invited to the event and asked to contribute to delivering the invitation to the event via their networks.

We decided to have Lyyti as a platform for registration to the event. The link to the registration form was opened just before Christmas, on December 19th, 2022. We used the registration form offered by the project

as a basis for our form. We added to the form a question about the participant's willingness to present his/her company or business in the event. In addition, we asked whether the participant would like to have a table to present, taste or sell his/her products.

2.6 Invitation of attendees and promotional activities implementation

The first invitations were sent out to attendees in December 2022, although the main promotional effort was carried out during January. This is due to Christmas time, since we thought that people are not very responsive during the holiday season, risking that people might not notice them.

The social media ad (in figure 2) was delivered through LinkedIn and Instagram. In addition, we asked the MAP of Finland to use their networks as well as social media channels to promote the event. Especially the association partners of the MAP like Finnish organic food association, Finnish glasshouse growers' association and fruit and berry growers' association were asked to do promotional activities to their network. In addition, the Finnish food sector coordination project informed their network about the event.

The producers were sent a personal invitation via email in which they were given a short description of the event and a link to the registration form. In addition, emails were attached by the pdf-file including the invitation and program (see figure 2) was attached. Since the event was held at the university campus, students were also invited to the event. This was done via information displays, placed in the lobbies of the university buildings.

3. Event implementation and outcomes

3.1 Event implementation

Even though the aim was to have purely a face-to-face meeting, there were a couple of sick cases including one of the event presenters, so we decided to accommodate online participation via MS Teams.

As described in chapter 2.1, we started the event with coffee during which the producers had a chance to set up their tables. Then we had presentations related to networking and cooperation in the food sector and how to foster SFSCs as well as introducing agroBRIDGES to the participants. After that producers participating in the event had a chance to present their business and experiences of the SFSC. After producers' presentations we had a couple presentations from retail about supporting SFSC and local food producers in their operation. In addition, we had a few company presentations related to SFSC platform, package experience and labelling, and an app to offer information about the product for consumers.

After the presentations we had about an hour for networking and getting to know producers and companies that were present. In the end, the event (networking session) lasted two hours longer than originally planned.

Figure 6: agroBRIDGES presentation

Figure 7: Producers talks

Figure 8: Producers' products

Figure 9: Networking with the participants

3.2 Event participation

In total there were 33 people registered for the event. Unfortunately, due to the seasonal flu, a few people had to cancel their participation. So, in total there were 30 people present and the table 3 below describes their role. In addition, during the networking session two students came to see and discuss with the producers.

Table 3: Event participation

Audience type	No. of participants
Producers	10
Retailer	4
Developers	12
Companies	4
Total	30

4. Event Validation

4.1 Validation of event concept by participants

At the event we had a feedback form placed on everyone's seat and we asked them to give feedback on the event. However only 9 participants returned the form. The next day we sent the participants a thank you message and asked for feedback via Google form. As a result, we had one more response. This means that in total we had feedback only from 10 participants, see table 4.

Table 4: Event validation

Question	Absolutely agree	Agree	Do not agree or disagree	Disagree	Fully Disagree	No answer
Were you familiar with the concept of Short Food Supply Chains before this event?	6	-	1	-	3	-
Did you find this event informative, and it gave you insights on implementing SFSC?	4	5	1	0	0	0
Did you find this event helpful for getting to know local producers, their methods, and efforts to bring local food closer to you?	3	6	1	0	0	0
Did you find the event helpful to understand the value of local producers' food, various benefits for your health, the environment, and the society?	2	5	3	0	0	0
Did you find enough information about how and where to buy local food from the producers or other businesses you've met?	10	0	0	0	0	0
Would you like another similar event to be organised in your region? How often?	8	0	0	0	0	2
Total	33	16	6	0	3	2

The Lyyti platform which we used for participant registration, automatically sent participants one question after the event: “Do you feel that you got value for your time? Share your thoughts with us so we can offer even better events in the future.” We got responses from 15 participants, and they seemed to be happy with the event, see figure 4.

Figure 10: Participants’ responses about the event gathered by Lyyti platform

Responses

Response rate	50%
Sent	30
Responded	15

4.2 Validation of “Let’s meet!” guidelines and templates by the organising partner

Question #1: Did you find the event concepts relevant to your local agri-food ecosystem and organisation?

Yes, the concepts guided us in selecting the event that was most suitable for our networks and season of the year, as well as arranging the event itself.

Question #2: Would you organise the same event again in your region? If yes, would you make any adjustments?

Yes, we would like to organise a producer event again. We got very positive feedback especially from the producer site and they were very happy to meet each other but also gain some information from other perspectives (retail, companies, research). It is quite challenging to reach producers to participate in the events in general, so there is a need to find means to reach them as well as organising events in collaboration with others. In addition, there might be better chances to involve different stakeholders if the event is organised in the afternoon/evening.

Question #3: Did you find the guidelines and templates sufficient for your event organization needs?

Yes, the templates were a very helpful base for planning the content and sharing invitations e.g., through social media.

Question #4: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines accurate enough to plan effectively?

Yes, the instructions were clear, and it was enough. In some cases, there might be a need to apply the instructions to better fit one's purposes.

Question #5: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines flexible enough to create an event tailored to your ecosystem/business needs?

Yes, the instructions were flexible, there was freedom to give a particular approach to the event.

4.3 Limitations and barriers of the organising partner

The low number of the consumers participating in the event might influence how useful producers experienced the event. Due to the remote location of the venue, there were not many options to have consumers invited.

In Finland wintertime limits the possibilities to arrange these kinds of events, since they must be organised indoors. There are more options for different types of events during summertime. In addition, gathering feedback from participants was a bit challenging even if both on-site and on-line forms were offered.

4.4 Suggestions for improvement of the concept and guidelines

Question #5: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines flexible enough to create an event tailored to your ecosystem/business needs?

Yes, the instructions are very flexible and give you freedom to apply those for your events.

5. Conclusions

Organising the event in collaboration with the other project was very fruitful. It also helped us to contact participants, especially the producers. However, it was not very easy to get producers to participate in the event. The event itself was very successful and we got very positive feedback from the participants. In addition to the presentations, the networking session and possibility to meet each other and to have free discussions were experienced to be very successful. The participants were willing to have similar events to be organised once or twice a year.